

Abstract

Tongue Diagnosis as a Valid and Reproducible Method in Clinical TCM Practice.

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Abstract

Part I: This paper addresses tongue diagnosis as a valid and reproducible method for establishing a logical and rational diagnosis within the framework of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM). Beyond its diagnostic value, tongue observation serves as an objective tool for evaluating therapeutic outcomes and guiding the ongoing course of treatment.

Based on 30 years of clinical data, including photographic documentation of each patient's tongue at every consultation, this approach reveals previously unrecognized applications of tongue diagnosis in everyday clinical practice. Multiple case histories provide insight into how consistent tongue imaging can enhance diagnostic accuracy, objectify treatment effects, and refine therapeutic strategies. This report emphasises the role of tongue diagnosis as a valid, reliable, and reproducible method in TCM.

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Part II: This method serves as a practical guide for TCM practitioners to reach a clear, logical, and rational diagnosis using tongue photography and patient histories. It acts as a bridge between TCM and scientific, allopathic medicine, providing an explanation for each change in the tongue from both perspectives.

Through this comprehensive guide, practitioners can follow step-by-step directions to identify and understand all significant tongue changes, enabling them to arrive at an effective diagnosis and rational therapy for any patient. Therapeutic success is continuously monitored through before-and-after tongue images, clearly documenting the progress of the treatment.

Keywords: Tongue Diagnosis; Clinical TCM; Allopathic Medicine; Therapeutic Monitoring.

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